

Mechanistic aspects of oxidation of alanine by Os^{VIII} in aqueous alkaline medium. A kinetic model

M. B. Yadav^a, Vijay Devra^b and Ashu Rani^{c*}

^aP.G. Department of Chemistry, Govt. College Kota, Kota-324 001, Rajasthan, India

^bP.G. Department of Chemistry, Govt. J. D. B. Girls' College, Kota-324 001, Rajasthan, India

^cDepartment of Pure and Applied Chemistry, Kota University, Kota-324 005, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : ashu.uok@gmail.com

Manuscript received 20 July 2009, revised 17 May 2010, accepted 17 May 2010

Abstract : Kinetics of oxidation of alanine by osmium(VIII) was studied in alkaline medium at 25 °C. The reaction was found to have first order dependence each in [Os^{VIII}] and [alanine] and second order in [OH⁻], which changed to zero order at higher concentration of [OH⁻]. The main product of the oxidation is the corresponding aldehyde. Temperature variation has also been studied for calculating different activation parameters. Spectroscopic evidence for the complex formation between Os^{VIII} and substrate was obtained from a UV-Visible spectra of Os^{VIII}, alanine and mixture of both. A plausible mechanism has been proposed to account for the experimental results.

Keywords : Kinetics, oxidation, alanine, osmium(VIII).

Introduction

The kinetics of oxidation of alanine by a number of oxidants viz. hexacyanoferrate¹, diperiodatoargentate [Ag^{III}]², *N*-bromoacetamide³ in alkaline medium and chloramine-T⁴, cerium(IV)⁵, KMnO₄⁶, tetrabutylammoniumtribromide (TBATB)⁷, dichloramine-T⁸ in acidic medium have been reported. OsO₄ has been extensively used as oxidising agent as well as a catalyst in the oxidation of variety of organic⁹ and inorganic compounds¹⁰. Various amino acids have been studied with different oxidants using osmium as a catalyst¹¹⁻¹⁵. Reviewing the catalytic role of Os^{VIII} in oxidation of amino acid and some other redox reactions^{16,17}, it is observed that the mechanism of catalysis depends on nature of the substrate, the oxidant and experimental conditions. The Os^{VIII} catalyzes the reaction by involving in mechanistic pathway by forming complexes with the reactants oxidising the substrate itself or through the free radical¹⁸. Os^{VIII} catalysis involves several complexes with different oxidation states of osmium. As Os^{VIII} has rarely been studied as oxidising agent for amino acids, we have selected the study of kinetics of oxidation of neutral amino acid i.e. alanine by Os^{VIII} and to propose a mechanism of formation and decomposition of different complexes during the reaction using UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Results and discussion

The concentration of [Os^{VIII}] was varied from 5.0 × 10⁻⁵ to 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentration of [Ala] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 1.2 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, *I* = 1.0 mol dm⁻³ at 25 °C. The pseudo-first order rate constant (*k'*) increases with increasing [Os^{VIII}]. The concentration of alanine was varied from 1.0 × 10⁻³ to 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at three concentration of [Os^{VIII}] viz. 0.5 × 10⁻⁴, 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ and 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 1.2 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, *I* = 1.0 mol dm⁻³ at 25 °C. The plot of (*k'*) versus [Ala] was linear passing through the origin indicating first order with respect to alanine. The concentration of [OH⁻] was varied from 1.2 × 10⁻² to 10.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentration of [Os^{VIII}] = 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [Ala] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, *I* = 1.0 mol dm⁻³ at 25 °C. The plot of log *k'* versus [OH⁻] indicates second and zero order dependence of rate on concentration of alkali at [OH⁻] ≤ 0.04 *M* and > 0.04 *M* respectively. Ionic strength was varied from 0.5 to 2.5 mol dm⁻³. The rate slightly increases with increase in ionic strength. No significant effect of ionic strength on the rate of reaction was observed. The reaction was studied at different temperature (20–40 °C) at fixed concentration of [Os^{VIII}] = 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [Ala] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 1.2 × 10⁻²

Table-1 (contd.)

1.0	10.0	24.81	2.48
2.0	1.0	3.42	3.42
2.0	2.0	6.43	3.21
2.0	3.0	9.64	3.21
2.0	4.0	12.62	3.15
2.0	5.0	15.65	3.13
2.0	6.0	18.84	3.14
2.0	7.0	21.95	3.13
2.0	8.0	25.02	3.12
2.0	9.0	28.03	3.11
2.0	10.0	31.18	3.12

Above mentioned mechanism is supported by previously reported two different works, firstly oxidation of glycolic acid catalysed by Os^{VIII} and oxidized by hexacyanoferrate in alkaline medium²³ and secondly uncatalysed oxidation of glycolic acid by Os^{VIII}²⁴. Mechanistic pathway of both these studies involve Os^{VIII} in the complexed form as osmate ion which reacts with alanine to form a complex which in a fast step, produces reaction products and other osmium complex with Os in +6 oxidation state. In case of oxidation by Os^{VIII}, Os accompanied by the reaction product remains in +6 complex state after the completion of the reaction (eqs. 10–11) but in the catalytic reaction, Os^{VI} further reacts with the oxidant to produce Os^{VIII} (eqs. 12–13).

Spectroscopic evidence for the complex formation between Os^{VIII} and substrate was obtained from a UV-Visible spectra of Os^{VIII}, alanine and a mixture of both. In alkaline medium when OH⁻ reacts with Os^{VIII}, osmate ions are formed²⁵ in a fast step which is evident from the

appearance of dark yellow colour immediately. Fig. 1(a) shows the UV-Visible spectra of alanine free alkaline Os^{VIII} solution. A peak at 255 nm corresponds to the presence

Fig. 1. The UV-Visible spectra of (a) alanine free alkaline Os^{VIII} solution and Os^{VIII}-alanine-OH⁻ systems, (b) 2 min after mixing, (c) after 15 min and (d) after 3 h at 25 °C.

of osmate ion. The spectra of the reaction mixture recorded after two minutes [Fig. 1(b)] of mixing Os^{VIII}, alanine and KOH show that two additional peaks appeared at 310 and 410 nm in addition to one observed at 255 nm. After 15 min, peaks at 410 and 240 nm reached to maximum absorbance [Fig. 1(c)] and the colour of the solution changed from yellow to dark purple. This colour persisted till the end of the reaction and on recording the spectra after 3 h, the peak at 255 and 310 nm almost disappeared and absorbance was also decreased at 410 nm showing the decomposition of adduct [Fig. 1(d)]. A typical kinetic run between absorbance and time is recorded at 410 nm, which shows formation of the adduct at initial time and thereafter its decomposition. So in present case studied kinetic reaction corresponds to decomposition of Os-alanine adduct. The rate equation explains first order kinetics in [alanine] and [Os^{VIII}]. The concentration of the reactive species is given in eq. (5) would depend on [OH⁻]² up to a certain limit beyond which the whole of OsO₄ will exist as [OsO₄(OH)₂]²⁻. This explains second and zero order dependence on [OH⁻]. The activation parameters Δ*E*, Δ*S*[‡], Δ*G*[‡] were evaluated from the plot of log *k*_{obs} vs 1/*T* and were found to be 9.14 kcal mol⁻¹, -79.9 cal K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ and 23.8 kcal mol⁻¹ respectively. As expected aggregation should greatly reduce the entropy, therefore negative values of Δ*S*[‡]²⁶ lend additional support to the rate determining step.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade and double distilled water was used throughout the study. A solution of alanine (Sisco, Chem. Ltd.) was prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount of recrystallized sample in double distilled water. $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ solution was prepared by dissolving OsO_4 (Johnson Matthey) in $0.125 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ KOH which was standardized iodometrically and stored in a refrigerator. KNO_3 (1.0 M) is used to maintain the ionic strength.

Kinetic measurements :

The kinetic measurements were performed on a Shimadzu UV 1601 spectrophotometer. The kinetics was followed under pseudo-first order condition where $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] < [\text{Amino acid}]$ at 25°C . The reaction was initiated by mixing alanine in temperature equilibrated alkali oxidant. KNO_3 was added for maintaining the ionic strength. Os^{VIII} concentration in aliquot (1.0 M) were analysed spectrophotometrically at 410 nm. Rate constants were calculated from the slope of $\log(\text{concentration})$ vs time plots and were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$. Activation parameters, e.g. ΔE , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger were also computed.

Stoichiometry :

Different sets of reaction mixtures containing varying ratios of Os^{VIII} to alanine where $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] < [\text{Amino acid}]$ in presence of constant amount of OH^- and KNO_3 were kept in a closed vessel. The concentration of Os^{VIII} was estimated spectrophotometrically at 410 nm. The results indicate one mole of alanine consumed two moles of Os^{VIII} .

The main oxidation products were identified as aldehyde by Tollens reagent, ammonia by Nessler's reagent and CO_2 was qualitatively detected by bubbling nitrogen gas through the acidified reaction mixture and passing the liberated gas through tube containing lime water.

Test for free radicals :

Reaction solutions were degassed with N_2 before the initiation of the reaction and the addition of acrylonitrile to the partially oxidized reaction mixtures. No polymerisation of the monomer was noted over a considerable

period of time. This experiment, however does not prove that a free radical is not formed. It is possible that the monomer might not be polymerized if the free radical reacts more quickly with one of the species present in the solution than with the monomer. However, in the knowledge that $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ undergoes a two electron change in the oxidation of organic compounds, it might not be erroneous to assume the absence of free-radicals.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Mr. K. M. Tandon and Mr. Yagnesh K. Gupta, DSCL, Kota for providing UV-Visible facilities and also thankful to Prof. K. S. Gupta, Rajasthan University, Jaipur for valuable suggestions.

References

1. P. K. Chourasia, N. C. Bhattacharjee and T. K. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 364; R. C. Acharya, N. K. Saran, S. R. Rao and M. N. Das, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1981, **14**, 143.
2. Changying Song, Lei Chen and Jinhuan Shan, *Research Lett. in Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, Article ID 786857, 4 pages.
3. M. Komal Reddy, Ch. Sanjeeva Reddy and E. V. Sundaram, *Tetrahedron*, 1985, **41**, 15, 3071.
4. Neeti Grover, Neelu Kambo and Santosh K. Upadhyay, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 2482.
5. V. Devra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 294.
6. Rafat M. Hassan, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1991, **69**, 2018.
7. Raghvendra Shukla, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2004, **116**, 101.
8. T. Gowda and J. M. Rao, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, **62**, 3303.
9. U. S. Mehrotra and S. P. Mushran, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1970, **48**, 1148; Puttaswamy and Nirmala Vaz, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2003, **28**, 409; S. Ananda, T. Demappa and N. M. M. Gowda, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1999, **29**, 737; B. L. Chandwani and G. D. Meghnani, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 560; Sushma Gupta, Vazid Ali and Santosh K. Upadhyay, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1989, **21**, 315.
10. Latika Bhatt, Prem Sharma, D. S. Gupta and Yugul K. Gupta, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, **12**, 2653; Ramgopal Bhattacharya and Alok Mohan Saha, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 85.
11. R. N. Mehrotra, R. C. Kapoor and S. K. Vajpai, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 999.
12. Veeresh Seregar, T. M. Veeresh and Sharanappa T. Nandibewoor, *J. Mol. Catal. (A) : Chemical*, 2007, **271**, 253.

Yadav *et al.* : Mechanistic aspects of oxidation of alanine by Os^{VIII} in aqueous alkaline *etc.*

13. T. P. Jose, S. T. Nandibewoor and S. M. Tuwar, *J. Sulfur Chem.*, 2006, **27**, 25.
14. Nagaraj P. Shetti, Raghunatharaddi R. Hosamani and S. T. Nandibewoor, *Research Lett. in Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, Article ID 786857, 5 pages.
15. T. Demappa and S. Ananda, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1999, **11**, 375.
16. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, India, 2nd ed., 1966.
17. Ramalingaiah, R. V. Jagadeesh and Puttaswamy, *J. Mol. Catal. (A)*, 2007, **265**, 70.
18. P. Veerasomaiah, K. B. Reddy, B. Sethuram and T. N. Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 402.
19. R. D. Sauerbrum and E. B. Sandell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4170.
20. W. P. Griffith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 245.
21. D. Mohan and Y. K. Gupta, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1085.
22. J. Nyilasi and P. Somogyi, *Acta Chim. Acad. Hung.*, 1973, **75**, 405.
23. G. C. Soni, B. L. Chandwani and G. D. Menghani, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 693.
24. B. L. Chandwani and G. D. Menghani, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 560.
25. Ramalingaiah, R. V. Jagadeesh and Puttaswamy, *Catalysis Communications*, 2008, **9**, 1443.
26. A. A. Frost and R. G. Pearson, "Kinetics and Mechanism", Wiley, New York, 1962, 101.

